

digitise

Brand Guidelines

www.australo.org

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Brand Strategy

Vision

DIGITISE envisions a future where consumers and prosumers are digitally empowered, actively engaged in energy activities and markets, and play a pivotal role in the global energy transition.

Our commitment lies in fostering digital literacy, sustainability, and security while driving positive change in the energy landscape.

By integrating advanced technologies such as Innovative Cross-Sector Services, Digital Twins, DLT-enabled Marketplaces, AI Analytics, and Big Data Management, we aim to empower individuals to make informed decisions, optimize energy usage, and contribute to a more resilient and sustainable world.

Mission

Our mission is to integrate cutting-edge technologies, including Innovative Cross-Sector Services, Digital Twins, DLT-enabled Marketplaces, AI Analytics, and Big Data Management, into a holistic consumer empowerment framework.

Through extensive validation in a well-established Living Lab and large-scale demonstration sites across Greece, Spain, Croatia, and Ireland, we aim to empower consumers, prosumers, and business actors (Retailers/Aggregators/LECs) with the tools they need to navigate diverse energy systems, cross-domain data sources, and multi-variate climatic and socio-economic conditions.

Our commitment lies in fostering digital literacy, sustainability, and security while driving positive change in the energy landscape.

Target Audience

Target persona 1

Gender: Female

Age: 32

Profession: Environmental consultant

Education: Master's degree in Environmental Science

Interests: Renewable energy sources, sustainable living, community engagement, climate action

Challenges: Balancing work, family, and environmental advocacy, navigating complex energy systems, understanding digital tools for energy management

Behavior: Active on social media platforms advocating for green initiatives, attends local sustainability workshops and events, seeks practical solutions to reduce her carbon footprint

Target persona 2

Gender: Male

Age: 28

Profession: Software developer

Education: Bachelor's degree in Computer Science

Interests: Smart home automation, blockchain technology, data analytics, energy efficiency, digital marketplaces

Challenges: Integrating various smart devices at home, finding reliable energy data sources, optimizing energy usage through technology

Behavior: Regularly reads tech blogs and follows industry trends, participates in hackathons and open-source projects, enjoys experimenting with IoT devices

Target persona 3

Gender: Male

Age: 45

Profession: Community organizer

Education: High school diploma

Interests: Empowering local residents, social justice, civic engagement, energy affordability, digital inclusion

Challenges: Bridging the digital divide in underserved communities, advocating for equitable energy policies, mobilizing community members for collective action

Behavior: Organizes neighborhood meetings and workshops, collaborates with local schools and nonprofits, believes in the power of grassroots movements

Personality

Archetypes

Brand archetypes are powerful tools used to define a brand's personality and create a distinctive identity. Derived from universal stories, values, and characters, these archetypes resonate with our collective consciousness.

By aligning our brand with an archetype, we can connect emotionally with our audience and stand out in a remarkable way, by utilizing a tone of voice that is appropriate for the recipients of our messages.

The Sage

Description: The Sage archetype embodies profound knowledge, wisdom, and a thirst for understanding. Sages are the venerable mentors, the keepers of ancient scrolls, and the seekers of truth. They guide others through their sagacity and share insights that illuminate the path forward.

Alignment with DIGITISE

Empowerment through Knowledge: Like a Sage, the DIGITISE project seeks to empower consumers and prosumers. It recognizes that digital literacy is the key to active participation in energy markets. Just as Sages impart wisdom, DIGITISE provides tools for understanding complex energy systems.

Informed Decision-Making: Sages encourage discernment. Similarly, DIGITISE equips users with knowledge about energy transactions, flexibility services, and digital ecosystems. By making informed choices, consumers can actively shape the energy transition.

The Magician

Description: The Magician archetype embodies transformation, innovation, and the ability to wield unseen forces. Magicians are alchemists, turning base elements into gold. They challenge the status quo, pushing boundaries to create something new and awe-inspiring.

Alignment with DIGITISE

Energy Alchemy: Like a Magician, DIGITISE transforms the energy landscape. It wields cutting-edge technologies to empower consumers. By creating digital twins, enabling DLT-based marketplaces, and using AI analytics, it turns complexity into accessible solutions.

Navigating Change: Magicians thrive on change. Similarly, DIGITISE navigates the energy transition. It adapts to diverse data sources, climatic variations, and socio-economic factors. Just as Magicians harness unseen forces, DIGITISE empowers users to shape their energy future.

Visual Tools

Logo

Main version

Logo

Secondary versions

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Color

Introduction to the selected color palette for a brand

The brand's color scheme includes the primary, secondary, accent (or exception to use in case of an error), and neutral colors such as white or grey.

The primary color is the most dominant and recognizable color of the brand, followed by the secondary colors that complement and contrast with the primary color.

The secondary colors are ordered according to the priority indicated in the diagram on the right, where the top color has higher priority than the bottom color.

Refer to the diagram on the right for specific colors.

Oxford Blue ^{Primary}

#0F1F4C
R15 G31 B76
C80 M59 Y0 K70

Mountain Meadow ^{Primary}

#1CC993
R28 G201 B147
C86 M0 Y27 K21

White ^{Neutral}

#FFFFFF
R255 G255 B255
C0 M0 Y0 K0

Aquamarine ^{Secondary}

#92FCC7
R146 G252 B199
C42 M0 Y21 K1

Black ^{Neutral}

#000000
R0 G0 B0
C60 M40 Y40 K100

Pastel Purple ^{Accent}

#9D8DF1
R157 G141 B241
C35 M42 Y0 K6

Blue-Gray ^{Texts}

#627089
R98 G112 B137
C28 M18 Y0 K46

Color

Gradient table

Specification of the gradient table

The gradient table indicates which neutral color (black or white) to use for writing text based on the percentage of opacity.

Refer to the adjacent table for more information.

100%	100%	100%	100%	100%
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80%	80%	80%	80%	80%
60%	60%	60%	60%	60%
40%	40%	40%	40%	40%
20%	20%	20%	20%	20%

Typography

Title

The font displayed is intended for use only in titles and subtitles.

Aa

Titles

[Download here](#)

Space Grotesk Bold

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Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

0123456789
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Typography

Aa Bb

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Paragraph

The font displayed on the page is intended for use in paragraphs only.

[Download here](#)

DM Sans Regular

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Jj Kk Ll Mm Nn Oo Pp Qq Rr
Ss Tt Uu Vv Ww Xx Yy Zz

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Mockups

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Title Example

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Title Example

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Title Example

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Brand Guidelines

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